

Mathematical Videos & Affiliated Supplementaries in TIB's AV Portal

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TIB's AV Portal

What is TIB's AV-Portal?

TIB's AV-Portal is a free web-based portal for scientific audiovisual media (focusing on engineering and science).

<https://av.tib.eu>

What does TIB's AV-Portal offer? - Content

- Conference talks: Gauß Prize Lecture
- Lectures: IHÈS Summer School Lecture in Analytic Number Theory
- Video Abstracts: Exploring Video Abstracts in Science Journals
- Interviews: Dirac and Hund on Symmetry in Relativity (and more)
- Experiments: Creating water vortices
- Simulations: Simulations in Chaos Theory

What does TIB's AV-Portal offer? - Services

- Digital Object Identifier (DOI) assignment
- Digital Preservation
- Automated Video Analysis
- Metadata Enrichment
- Crosslinking to related information

What does TIB's AV-Portal offer? - Workflow

Mathematical Media Packages

Mathematical Media Packages (1/2)

How research projects are comprehensively published today

- Project FLOW
- MSRI Workshop
- Fabio Galasso's scientific work

There are

- films
- journal publications
- source code
- statistical evaluations, and so much more...

Mathematical Media Packages (2/2)

We found four main categories of mathematical videos with additional material attached:

1. Visual Simulation Data
2. Video Abstracts
3. Conference Recordings
4. Lecture Videos

Visual Simulation Data (1/2)

What does this image tell you ...

The screenshot shows the TIB AV-Portal interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Search for people, places, topics..." and a "Search" button. Below the search bar, the main content area displays a video player. The video player shows a comparison of particle size distributions simulated by three models: the sectional model (FS1000), the log-normal distribution model (LN), and the combined power law and log-normal distribution model (PL+LN). The video player includes a progress bar and a citation of the segment: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5446/18564#t-00:02:00:11>.

Automated Media Analysis **BETA**

Recognized Entities | Speech transcript

Search...

- Speech
- Text in the video
- Image content

<https://av.tib.eu/media/18564?933>

... without context information?

Video Abstracts (1/2)

What material is to be expected in the wake of video abstracts?

A screenshot of the Elsevier website's "Video Abstracts" section. The page features a left-hand navigation menu with options like "Search for Authors", "Submit Your Paper", "Track Your Paper", "Order Journal", and "View Articles". Below this is a "Journal Metrics" section with links for "Scopus Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP)", "Change Journal Rank (CJR)", "Impact Factor", and "Year Impact Factor". The main content area is titled "Video Abstracts" and lists several mathematical topics, each with a video thumbnail, a title, a "Watch Video Abstract" link, and a "Read full article here" link. The topics include: "Sets characterized by missing sums and differences in dilating polytopes", "Newman's conjecture in function fields", "On sets with small additive doubling in product sets", "Bits of p -primes in binary, Wieferich primes and a conjecture of Erdős", and "On number of partitions of an integer into a fixed number of positive integers".

Conference Recordings (1/2)

Is a video recording of a conference talk more than just a nice add-on?

The image displays a composite of three web interface elements. On the left is a 'TIB-PORTAL' page featuring a video player with a speaker and a title: 'The dichotomy between structure and randomness, arithmetic progressions, and the primes'. In the center is a 'CiteSeerX' page for the same title, showing the abstract and metadata. On the right is a search interface with a search bar and navigation links. Two large red arrows point from the video player and the search interface towards the CiteSeerX page, indicating a workflow or integration.

Conference Recordings (2/2)

- Detailed explanations.
- Slides accompanied by words.
- Questions and discussions.
- Soft factors such as posture, gesture, voice have a didactic value.

Lecture Videos (1/2)

The value of blackboard and Khan Style.

Outlook

Outlook (2/2)

- Defining relations.
- Automated indexing to interlink associated information of a research project (or related projects).
- Creating and maintaining thematic web archives (on demand).

Linking Mathematical Software
in Web Archives

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Contact, Discussion, Questions

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<https://xkcd.com/1256/>